

UNRAVELING AN IMMIGRANT'S JOURNEY AND DECODING THE EXPERIENCE THROUGH SELECT POEMS

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ABSTRACT

Immigrant Literature is a branch of interest that is gaining popularity and concern in the huge arena of English Literature. The reasons for mass immigration generally are political, economical or social upheavals that turn an individual's life completely topsy-turvy. Ha Jin, the Chinese _American poet in his poem, *I Sing of an Old Land* addresses this condition as a “timeless curse”, a term that aptly describes the situation of the forcefully displaced people who suddenly encounter loss of identity, nationality and a threat to their very existence. In a final bid to survive and stay alive, they flee for their dear lives with their families only to encounter horrendous situations that force them to understand the meaning of immigration and the status of an immigrant. For some of us who have witnessed mass migration forcing many to abandon their homes in recent times, the trauma that they undergo can be understood only when we hear it from the mouth of the survivors, and this is where literature helps us. Several authentic voices of

representation have recorded their nightmarish experiences through poems and novels. This paper concentrates on a few select poems penned by such survivors and tries to understand and empathize with them. By uncovering the uncertainty and alienation felt by the immigrants in the host land, this paper aims to portray how they struggle to free themselves from the nostalgic trap of their homeland, come to terms with their now new status of ‘refugee’, their decision to look forward, acclimate to new surroundings and find survival techniques in the wake of hostility and violence. As the paper traces a journey of profound loss and silent endurance, it puts forth a very important question, what does one do when “home chases you” away and tries to find answers to this heart wrenching query through five representative poems.

Key words: *Immigration, home, new lands, survival, acclimatization*

One of the major concerns that is alarmingly gathering momentum and disrupting normal life across the world in recent times is the mass exodus of asylum seekers from various nations across the world holding on desperately to their dear lives and families, crossing borders through legal or illegal means and methods to become refugees in a foreign land. The UNHCR (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees) claims that this global forced displacement worldwide is “a result of persecution, conflict, generalized violence, or human rights violation”. Whatever may be the cause, what we need to understand is that the act of immigration is not something new but is as old as humanity itself. The variation lies in the cause and its terrifying consequences that mainly target innocent civilians, though of course, the problem lies within or among the high-level bureaucracy.

If we were to analyze the migratory tendency of man, all that we must do is turn the pages of history to our Ancients who dwelt deep within the forests with no thought of competition, challenge or notion of domination. Certain factors like climatic changes, natural disasters and other related aspects must have forced them to move out of their wild settings in search of better pastures and a secure life. Having found fertile grounds and favorable conditions of environment, they must have huddled together in groups and each unit must have evolved its own tradition and culture, adopted and practiced similar rituals, embraced identical beliefs, formulated a set of rules and regulations to be implemented among their people, thus leading to the emergence of ethnic communities and flourishing civilizations that thrived within ear-marked territorial boundaries. In course of time, as man evolved from being primeval to being civilized, it must have also created an upheaval in his thought patterns, emotional responses, and consequent actions. Soon eyeing and prying into each other's living, the need to control and dominate raising its ugly fangs must have resulted in dissension, clashes, strife, wars, massacres and genocides. This act has reached a point of severe crisis in contemporary times due to technology oriented cunning strategies of war that threaten the safety and security of human lives.

It is necessary to note that if migration is practiced as a voluntary movement in search of betterment, nobody complains; but when forced displacement happens, it deprives the individual of their nationality and citizenship and along with it a sense of apprehension, fear and trauma completely encompasses them. The UNHCR (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees) statistics 2022 has estimated that by the end of 2023, approximately 117.2 million people would be rendered homeless and stateless, seek asylum as refugees in other lands and many millions would be brutally massacred within and outside their homelands.

Cathy Caruth's famed definition of trauma in her *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma and the possibility of History* states that "Trauma is an overwhelming experience of sudden, or catastrophic events, in which the response to the event occurs in the often delayed and uncontrolled repetitive occurrence of hallucinations and other intensive phenomena" (81). An immigrant forced to contemplate migration to unknown shores due to dire circumstances in his own country finds that his sense of secure well-being is breached which inevitably results in psychic ordeals. It is here that Literature steps in to provide a cathartic platform to many individuals who have expressed their pain and agony in generic classifications of poetry, novel, short stories or non-fiction.

Under the broad umbrella term 'Traumatic Literature', immigrant writing occupies a specific space of interest today. It reflects the harrowing experience of immigration from known familiar terrains to unknown unfamiliar territories either through legal, documented methods or as illegal, undocumented aliens. Immigrant Literature tries to provide answers to interested readers about their traumatic exits from homelands, their entry into new lands, their acculturation, assimilation, adoption and adaptation to new environments or their diasporic struggles. To prove this point, five poems have been taken up for analysis in this paper because the researcher here feels that there is a step by step process that accompanies forced immigration – escaping violence and death in one's homeland, crossing the borders into a new land, trying to suppress memories, coming to terms with circumstances and adapting, adopting, acclimatizing to new culture, language and tradition. In this connection, Warsan Shire's *Home*, Ae Hee Lee's *Conversation with an Immigration Officer*, Amineh Abou Karech's *Lament for Syria*, Tishani Doshi's *The Immigrant's Song* Ha Jin's *I Sing of an Old Land*, are discussed in detail to substantiate the claim of phased process.

In the first poem *Home*, Warsan Shire, a British writer, does not mince words when she portrays the stark reality of how homeland is no longer a safe haven that offers shelter, comfort and security, but is “the mouth of a shark” (Warsan, line 2) and “the barrel of a gun”(56). In 1991, when Somalian Civil war erupted, the military regime of President Mohamed Siad Barre was crushed, but other factions and clans started warring for power. In this Civil War, it is assumed that while more than 25,000 were killed, roughly about one and a half million people fled the country. Warsan Shire’s family too was one among those who escaped to England. She learnt about her roots from her uncle who spoke about “the boarding house, sipping qaxwo – Somali coffee, spiced with cinnamon and cardamom – he told her, he felt that he had “failed at life” and “was cursed by the war.” {qtd in Okeowo, *Portraits*} She came to understand that the refugees had sought asylum in several countries that included United Kingdom and Italy. During one of her poetry reading visit to Italy, she met the immigrant community living in Rome and gathered first-hand information about their hopeless conditions of living. Inspired and deeply affected by what she saw and heard, that night she composed the poem *Home*.

Warsan Shire literally jolts the readers from their state of smug complacency when she verbally portrays how one’s neighbors flee for their dear lives on one side and on the other side, one’s clandestine lover stands with no love in his eye holding “a gun bigger than his body” (10) in his hand. This is the moment of realization that homeland is no longer a safe haven. Reduced to the status of an immigrant now, they tear up their passports” sobbing as each mouthful of paper/ made it clear that you wouldn’t be going back” (21 -22):

you have to understand,

that no one puts their children in a boat

unless the water is safer than the land

no one burns their palms

under trains beneath carriages

no one spends days and nights in the stomach of a truck

feeding on newspaper unless the miles travelled

means something more than the journey. (23 -30)

As they cross borders and enter new lands, the immigrants realize that they must gear up physically, mentally and spiritually to endure the humiliating slogans raised against them, words that never let them forget their refugee status:

go home blacks

refugees

dirty immigrants

asylum seekers

sucking our country dry

niggers with their hands out

they smell strange savage

messed up their country and now they want

to mess ours up (48-56)

The reader /listener, at this juncture wonders how the refugees would deal with the enormity of this loathing and hostility, when Warsan Shire provides a touching explanation as can be seen in the following lines:

maybe because the blow is softer
than a limb torn off
or the words are more tender than fourteen men between
your legs
or the insults are easier
to swallow
than rubble
than bone
than your child body
in pieces (59-68) .

Having crossed borders with broken hearts and anguished minds, the next stage in the immigration process is the interrogation by the authorities of the country where asylum is sought which is featured in the following poem *Conversation with Immigration Officer* that is taken up for discussion.

Ae Hee Lee's poem *Conversation with Immigration Officer* brings alive the pathos of this second stage, wherein she refers to the acute treatment meted out to the asylees in the famed Angel Island Immigration Station which functioned from January 21, 1910, and was razed down by fire in November, 1940. The poem refers to the immigrant population of the Russo- Japanese War of 1904. Propelled by the destruction caused by two powerful nations, many decided to flee from their native land to seek asylum and refuge in neighboring countries. As the woman in the poem sits in front of a grim immigration Officer to face an avalanche of queries, for, "The Officer has a catalog of potential question in her eyes" (*Conversation*), the reminiscing of the "paradise" that one was forced to leave begins – "the bright lime groves", "pearly remains of snow into my mouth / drop drop drop..." (*Conversation*), the native prophecies and whale songs. At the end of the harrowing interview, the Officer says "You will hear from them in a couple of months" (*Conversation*) and the asylee is sent back to the detention center with no near hope of crossing the borders to safety. After months and sometimes even years of detention, those who are lucky to be alive may eventually see the dawn in a new land to resettle and begin life anew, but their conscious mind would never steer clear of the memories of glorious old days that reaped love, laughter and respect as can be seen in the next poem by 13-year-old Aminah Abou Kerech's *Lament for Syria*.

The Syrian Civil War, one of the most devastating wars that twenty first century had ever seen was triggered by pro-democracy protests raised against the Syrian government led by President Bashar-al-Assad. What catapulted the growing unrest was the anti-regime graffiti paintings by a group of teenagers on the walls of their small hometown Daraa. When they were imprisoned, protests and demonstrations surfaced. The police and military forces brutally tried to

suppress them. Soon the conflict flared into a full-fledged civil war leaving more than 3,80,000 dead and 14 million Syrians, as per UNHCR statistics, had to flee from their homes.

Amineh Abou Kerech was just 13, when she was awarded the prestigious British Award for Young Poets in 2017 for her poem *Lament for Syria*. Her family had migrated from Darayya in Syria when war broke out. In Amineh's own words, "In Syria, all the time we were scared." (Fox, The Guardian). In 2016, when they entered England, she didn't know one word of English, but, by 2017, she had managed to learn the language enough to send in an entry for the Betjeman poetry contest. Even as she laments for the glorious culture of Syria that she had to leave behind, she gratefully acknowledges the safety and security United Kingdom, her now new homeland provides: "I feel so happy here because I have a future and things won't be scary anymore" (Fox, The Guardian) and again, "Everything will be good and we will always be in peace". (Fox, The Guardian).

In her poem, Amineh recalls with a nostalgic voice, the crooning doves of Syria, but immediately she is terrified by the memories of soldiers who "walk over my face" (Lament). Her young mind harkens to a land that respected elders, cherished hospitality as an indelible virtue, rejoiced in the beauty and serenity of nature and celebrated familial bonds:

I am from Syria

From a land where people pick up a discarded piece of bread

So that it does not get trampled on

From a place where a mother teaches her son not to step on an ant at the end of
the day.

From a place where a teenager hides his cigarette from his old brother out of respect.

From a place where old ladies would water jasmine trees at dawn.

From the neighbors' coffee in the morning

From: after you, aunt; as you wish, uncle; with pleasure, sister...(Lament)

Today Syria has seen enough destruction and is "still waiting for relief" (Lament). She struggles to "design a City of Love, Peace, Concord and Virtue / free of mess, war, wreckage and misery" (Lament) in poetic verse and poses this question:

Can anyone teach me

How to make a homeland?

Heartfelt thanks if you can (Lament)

These lines echo the anguish of having to run from one's country to safer shores. Though the immigrants have escaped from the rampages of war, they remain caught in a nostalgic trap that traumatizes them continually. Amineh's poem clearly underlines the intersectionality of two worlds – one that is ancestral and the other that is newfound which creates a diasporic turmoil, an idea that is reflected in Tishani Doshi's poem *The Immigrant's Song*.

Born in India to a Welsh mother and Gujarati father, Tishani Doshi moved to America for her Under graduation and Post graduation programs and later to London, spending many years working in the advertisement Department of Harper's and Queen Magazine. As a fiction writer and poet, she sympathizes and empathizes with the immigrants. She speaks of how they make a conscious attempt to suppress their painful loss of their motherland, and their resilience to silently endure the inevitable circumstance. Like Amineh, she records the immigrant's wistful recollection of his native land's glory when, "coffee beans filled the morning with hope" (*The*

Immigrant's Song). She speaks of how they make a conscious attempt to suppress their painful loss of their motherland, and their resilience to silently endure the inevitable circumstance. As asylees and refugees, they consciously and willfully decide not to retrace their steps and gulp down their anguished memories of how their homeland had abandoned them:

let us speak of our lives now—
the gates and bridges and stores.
let us not burden them with stories
of war or abandonment.
Let us not name our old friends
who are unravelling like fairy tales
in the forests of the dead.
Naming them will not bring them back.

Let us stay here, and wait for the future
to arrive, for grandchildren to speak
in forked tongues about the country
we once came from. (*The Immigrant's Song*).

To reconcile to one's situation, however tough it may be, is the first step towards progress and this is exactly what Xuefei Jin who writes under the pseudonym Ha Jin recommends in his poem *I Sing of an Old Land*.

Due to the turn of political events in China, especially at the Tiananmen Square in 1989, he arrived "at Logan airport from China with a suitcase and a duffel bag, a tattered assortment of dictionaries and a \$30 in his pocket" (Frank Gibney Jr.). Today he teaches at Boston University,

is a prolific writer who has bagged several prestigious literary awards like the Hemingway Award (1996), the Faulkner Award (1999), the Flannery O'Connor Award (1997). In an interview with Henry Ace Knight via email, when asked about his state of mind as he watched the events unfurl at the Tiananmen Square, he replied: "I was enraged. I had served in the People's Army. Now the army became butchers ... I saw a mother that ate her children".

In his poem, *I Sing of an Old Land*, (ISOL), Ha Jin highlights the violence and the betrayal by one's own countrymen that spews hatred and intolerance:

I sing of an old land
where the gods have taken shelter underground,
where the human idols eat human sacrifice, swords,
where truth is always a bloody legend.
where hatred runs the business of philanthropy,
where blazing dragons eclipse the wronged ghosts,

where silence and smiles are the trace of wisdom,
where words imitate spears and swords,
where truth is always a bloody legend. (*I Sing*)

In order to escape from this tormenting environment, there were only two options available to the people - "Like my ancestors who were scattered into the smoky winds, / who scrambled to leave home /or rushed towards the approaching enemies" (*I Sing*). Ha Jin's decision to leave China and seek life and livelihood elsewhere was the same as thousands of others,

who disappeared in other lands
bearing no hope but persistence, no honor but the story,

no fortune but parents and children,
singing a timeless curse,
a curse that has bound us together
and rooted us deep in the wreck
of our homeland. (*I Sing*)

But the minds of the immigrants do not relax or accept the sudden changes of scene and space. It continues to hover between reality and memory, trying earnestly to come to terms with the fact of the situation:

I touch the land at night—
My hands trace the map on the wall,
from mountains to villages and to rivers,
from plains to cities and to seashores. (*I Sing*)

Gradually they learn to accept their fate and look forward to resettling, rebuilding a new life in new lands, even though all the time their mind retraces its step to “weep for the old land” for “its profound stupidity” and for “its chaos and tenacity” that “seize our hearts and throats”.

From these five poems randomly chosen amongst a ton of immigrant literature, we understand that forced migration or immigration due to war, terrorism and economic reasons can leave devastating effects on the psyche of the asylees and refugees. Immigration poetry, while unraveling the traumatic experiences of immigrants offers a revelation of how man’s savage instincts force him to predate upon his fellow human beings, disrupting, destroying and degrading them. What one finally deciphers from these poems is that unless man’s notions and actions change, in this era of nuclear warfare and advanced scientific technologies, we may soon move towards extinction of humans. It’s now the right time to wake up and realize that we need

to go beyond time and space, language and culture, dissolve all differences and discriminations to stand as a unit to make this world a better place “to live, to love, to learn and leave a legacy” (Stephen Cowey) for generations to thrive on this beautiful planet.

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